

Inclusive Library Services for Deaf-Blind Students in Nigeria: A Critical Overview.

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Abstract

This paper explores inclusive library services for Deaf-Blind students in Nigeria. Providing library services to all users without discrimination is a primary goal of modern libraries. Therefore, this paper uses a conceptual review approach to examine the vital role libraries play in supporting inclusive education for deaf-blind individuals. It discusses the concept of deaf-blindness, a rare condition characterised by combined hearing and vision loss that restricts access to both auditory and visual information. This leads to challenges such as social isolation, limited access to information, and barriers to education and employment. The paper also examines the concept of inclusive education as a global movement aimed at ensuring equal access and participation in education for students often excluded due to various disabilities. Additionally, it reviews different models of inclusive library services for deaf-blindness, which are essential for promoting equal access to information and fostering national development; these include accessibility features, communication accommodations, assistive technologies, and services tailored for deaf-blind users. The benefits and challenges of inclusive library services for deaf-blind individuals are also discussed. Finally, the paper recommends that, among other measures, the Librarian Registration Council of Nigeria and the National Library of Nigeria, in collaboration with relevant authorities, should implement existing national standards for inclusive library services.

Keywords: Library services, Special needs users, Persons living with disabilities, Nigeria

Introduction

Libraries worldwide are tasked with providing information services that support society's education and research needs. This means that no meaningful formal education can occur without effective library services, which include current awareness, bibliographic, abstracting, indexing, and selective dissemination of information services, including those for Persons Living with Disability (PLWD). The World Health Organisation (WHO) (2022) defines Persons Living with Disability as individuals with long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments that, when combined with barriers, can prevent their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others. These may include physical disabilities (e.g., mobility, dexterity), intellectual disabilities (e.g., cognitive, learning), mental disabilities (e.g., psychiatric, emotional), chronic illnesses or conditions (e.g., diabetes, epilepsy), and sensory disabilities (e.g., visual, hearing, speech, deaf-blindness).

Deaf-blindness, also known as dual sensory impairment, is defined by Bethany (2023) as a condition where an individual experiences a combination of visual and auditory impairments, leading to significant challenges with communication, mobility, and daily life. Their communication is facilitated through tactile sign language, braille, large print, audio materials, assistive technology (e.g., screen readers, communication devices), and support personnel (e.g., interpreters, guides). They continually face issues

such as social isolation, limited access to information, and barriers to education and employment, among other challenges that require specialised services and attention. Library services for deaf-blindness have therefore become very crucial. The benefits are substantial and include promoting equal access to information, improving education and employment opportunities, and fostering social inclusion and community engagement. Consequently, the need to identify current barriers to library access for the deaf-blind and to explore how libraries can effectively offer inclusive services to this group has become essential. This paper, therefore, examines the vital role libraries play in supporting inclusive education for deaf-blind individuals by analysing existing frameworks, services, and challenges.

Deaf-blindness

Deaf-blindness is a rare condition where an individual experiences combined hearing and vision loss, which restricts access to both auditory and visual information. Texas Deaf-blind Outreach (2022) observed that when both senses are impaired, their combined effects create a barrier that blocks or distorts large amounts of information. This leads to a persistent problem in gathering information throughout a person's life. Students cannot learn what they do not perceive, and they may be unaware of what they are missing. Similarly, according to the National Centre on Deaf-blindness (2024), deaf-blindness spans a spectrum from mildly hard of hearing with mild visual impairment to completely deaf and blind, or a combination of severity in vision and hearing loss. It might seem that deaf-blindness means a total inability to see or hear. However, in reality, deaf-blindness is a condition in which the combination of hearing and visual impairments in children and youth causes “such severe communication and other developmental and educational needs that they cannot be accommodated in special education programmes solely for children with deafness or blindness,” or those with multiple disabilities (Blaha, 2001). Children identified as deaf-blind are distinguished educationally because impairments in sight and hearing require careful, specialised educational approaches to ensure they have the opportunity to reach their full potential. For those who can see and hear, the world extends outward as far as their eyes and ears can reach; for the young child who is deaf-blind, the world is initially much narrower. If the child is profoundly deaf and totally blind, their experience of the world extends only as far as their fingertips can reach. Such children are nearly alone if no one is touching them.

Typically, according to the Texas School for the Blind and Visually Impaired Outreach Program (2024), learning and development happen as children use their vision and hearing to engage with their surroundings. These distance senses enhance interaction with a world that exists beyond the limits of their physical bodies. Individuals can learn by watching others, observing objects and actions, and listening to voices and sounds. Depending on its severity, deaf-blindness affects a child's attraction to, interest in, and interaction with the environment.

Hence, Prickett & Welch (1995) observed that, without appropriate intervention, this limited access leads to isolation that affects an individual's development and learning. The more severe an individual's deaf-blindness, the narrower the world from which they can learn, and the more important the sense of touch becomes. Understanding this is the first step in helping an individual expand their learning beyond their reach. Libraries and librarians thus have a huge responsibility to play in the lives of the deaf-blind by ensuring the inclusiveness of education, as enshrined in the national policy on education.

Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is a worldwide movement aimed at ensuring equal access and participation in education for students who are often excluded due to differences such as disabilities, diverse ethnic and

linguistic backgrounds, and low socio-economic status. It involves reallocating quality educational opportunities, recognising and valuing differences, and making sure marginalised groups have a voice in decision-making processes that address their educational needs. Artiles & Kozleski (2007) defined inclusive education as a continuous effort towards (a) the redistribution of quality opportunities to learn and engage in educational programmes, (b) the recognition and appreciation of differences as reflected in content, pedagogy, and assessment methods, and (c) providing opportunities for marginalised groups to represent themselves in decision-making processes that challenge exclusion and influence solutions affecting their children's educational future. This concept of inclusive education as an ongoing effort highlights that we operate within dynamic contexts. The boundaries and centres of our work are in constant flux, creating new margins and centres.

Similarly, Roger & Gordon (2023) define inclusive education broadly as any policy, programme, or practice that aims to increase access, presence, participation, and success for all students in education. Consequently, efforts to identify and eliminate barriers to education for all students constitute inclusive education. It is as straightforward as it is complex. Since the advent of modern schooling, there have been successive attempts to understand how schooling affects different population groups, to expand provision to serve more students, and to improve their educational experiences and outcomes. Those with special educational needs must have access to mainstream schools that can accommodate them within a child-centred pedagogy capable of addressing their needs.

Regular schools with this inclusive approach, including library services, are the most effective way to combat discriminatory attitudes, foster welcoming communities, build an inclusive society, and achieve education for all. Moreover, they provide an effective education to the majority of children and enhance the efficiency and, ultimately, the cost-effectiveness of the entire system.

Theoretical Framework of Inclusive Library Services for Deaf-Blindness

An inclusive library is a vital community resource that meets the varied information needs of all community members. According to Grassi (2013), inclusion is an approach to library service that involves patrons with disabilities in an equitable manner. He further stated that if the library ensures everything is done to address the diverse needs of patrons with special needs, it is genuinely being inclusive. Inclusive library services for the deaf-blind are essential for promoting equal access to information and supporting national development. Therefore, this paper will focus on the Social Model of Disability.

Social Model of Disability

The Social Model of Disability was created by Mike Oliver, a British academic and disability rights advocate who popularised the term in 1983. He built on the pioneering work of the Union of the Physically Impaired Against Segregation (UPIAS) in the 1970s, which differentiated between impairment (a physical condition) and disability (a social limitation). According to the social model, 'disability' is socially constructed. Therefore, the social model views 'disability' as the outcome of the interaction between individuals living with impairments and an environment filled with physical, attitudinal, communication, and social barriers. This implies that the physical, attitudinal, communication, and social environment must change to enable people with impairments to participate in society on an equal basis with others.

A social model perspective recognises the reality of impairment and its effects on individuals. However, it advocates for adapting physical, attitudinal, communication, and social environments to accommodate impairment as a natural element of human diversity. Its goal is to transform society to better include people

living with impairment. It upholds the belief that people with disabilities deserve full participation and equal rights as citizens. The social model of disability is now globally acknowledged as the standard approach to understanding and addressing 'disability'. Similarly, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) signifies an official shift in attitudes and strategies concerning disability.

Application of the Social Model of Disability in Libraries

Applying this model requires transforming library spaces, services, and policies to be inclusive by design. Thus, this transformation can be done in the following areas, which are also in line with the models of inclusive library services for deaf blindness according to IFLA (2016), including:

1. **Accessibility features (e.g., braille, large print, audio materials):** Accessible Educational Materials, or Accessible Instructional Materials, are print and technology-based educational materials that include printed and electronic textbooks and related core materials that are designed or converted in a way that makes them usable across the widest range of student variability regardless of format (print, digital, graphical, audio, video). Students with visual impairments may require one or more specialised formats, including braille, large print, audio and/or digital. When specialised formats, paired with support for proper use, are matched to a student's unique learning needs and combined with effective instruction in reading, the result can mean the difference between exclusion and achievement across the curriculum. Libraries can make provision for physical accessibilities such as tactile signage and wayfinding, braille labels on shelves and materials, adaptive technology workstations, accessible seating and study areas, as well as provision for clear pathways and minimal clutter
2. **Communication accommodations (e.g., ASL interpreters, captioning):** Accommodations for students who are deaf or hard of hearing can be classified as "visual" and "aural." Visual accommodations rely on a person's sight; aural accommodations rely on a person's hearing abilities. Visual accommodations include sign language interpreters, lip reading, and captioning. Communicating with deaf and hard-of-hearing people is easy if you follow some basic principles and use communication access services such as interpreters or CART. The most important point to remember is to ask the deaf or hard-of-hearing person their preferences and tips they find helpful. Libraries can provide accommodations such as American Sign Language (ASL) interpreters, tactile sign language interpreters, braille and large-print materials, audio descriptions, captioning, and Video Remote Interpreting (VRI) services. While students, faculty, and staff, with or without disabilities, can benefit from live captioning, common accommodations for people with disabilities include Sign Language and interpreters. Having live captioning does not replace the need for a Sign Language Interpreter, as they address different needs.
3. **Assistive technology (e.g., screen readers, magnification software):** Assistive technology is equipment used by individuals with disabilities to promote independence. Deaf-blind individuals often use assistive technology, such as braille displays, screen readers, and specialised communication devices, to access online content. As technology is always changing and improving, so is the equipment. Devices that help the deaf, hard of hearing, and deaf-blind live independently include Frequency Modulation (FM) systems, amplified telephones, and alerting devices such as a vibrating or flashing alarm clock. Other assistive technology libraries adopt include: Screen readers and magnification software, Braille displays and embossers, Scanners with OCR software, Accessible databases and digital collections, as well as Assistive listening devices

4. Deaf-blind specific services (e.g., tactile sign language, braille): Tactile signing is a method of communicating using touch that's used by some children who have both a hearing loss and sight impairment. The deaf-blind child places their hands over the signer's hands to follow what's being communicated through touch and movement. Braille can help deaf-blind people access information in books and magazines, although it is not intended for use in one-on-one conversation. Some deaf-blind people choose to use Braille to communicate with others.
5. Staff Training and Support: For the sustainability of the models, it is pertinent for libraries to engage staff in disability awareness and sensitivity training, ASL and tactile sign language training, Braille and large print materials training, Assistive technology training and above all, partnership with deaf-blind organisations
6. Collection Development: Above all, libraries must make deliberate efforts at acquiring relevant materials that will support deaf-blindness as part of their collections. These materials include Braille and large print books, Audiobooks and digital audio materials, Accessible e-books and digital magazines, Tactile graphics and 3D printing, among other deaf-blind specific collections
7. Programs and services: It is also pertinent for libraries to, as a matter of policy, design programs and services that have a direct bearing on the lives of the deaf-blind. Programmes and services such as deaf-blind book clubs, Tactile art and craft programs, Braille and ASL storytelling, Accessible technology workshops, Community outreach and partnership programs, among others, will go a long way towards making library services more inclusive for the deaf-blind.

This model ensures that libraries provide inclusive services and accessible environments for deaf-blind individuals, promoting equal access to information and opportunities for social interaction.

Benefits of Inclusive Library Services for Deaf-Blindness

Inclusive library services for deaf-blindness provide enormous benefits, including individual, societal, educational, economic, library, and community benefits.

For individual benefits, inclusive library services for the deaf-blind will ensure equal access to information, enhanced literacy and education, increased independence, improved social interaction and community engagement, as well as emotional well-being and self-esteem of the deaf-blind (Ezeabasili & Umeji, 2021). Similarly, society will benefit from inclusive library services, as they promote inclusive and diverse communities, break down barriers and stigma, foster social justice and equality, enhance economic opportunities, and support human rights and dignity.

The educational benefits are clearly significant, as inclusive library services for deaf-blind individuals will provide greater access to educational resources, improved learning outcomes, increased accessibility to higher education, enhanced skills development (e.g., braille, ASL), and better preparedness for employment (IFLA, 2016).

Economically, it will boost employment opportunities, economic empowerment, reduce poverty and dependency, improve healthcare outcomes, and increase tax revenue and economic growth (Eskay & Chima, 2013).

The library also benefits from these services as they will enhance its reputation and credibility, increase patronage and engagement, improve staff training and awareness, optimise the use of resources and technology, and ensure compliance with accessibility standards and regulations (Ezeabasili & Umeji, 2021).

For the community, providing inclusive library services will raise awareness and understanding, reduce stigma and isolation, strengthen community cohesion, improve accessibility and inclusivity, and better support networks and services, among other community benefits.

Thus, providing inclusive library services would enable libraries to make a significant impact on the lives of deaf-blind individuals, promoting equal access to information, education, and social opportunities.

Challenges

Despite the significant benefits of providing inclusive library services for the deaf-blind, certain obstacles hinder the realisation of the library's goal to ensure its services reach everyone, regardless of social status. Ezeabasili & Umeji (2021) and Igwela & Opela (2020) outlined these challenges as follows:

1. **Physical and Environmental Challenges:** this has to do with the inaccessible library buildings and layouts, as well as the inability of libraries to provide sufficient braille and tactile signage, inadequate lighting and acoustics, among other limited adaptive technologies.
2. **Communication and language barriers** such as limited American Sign Language (ASL) and tactile sign language interpreters, insufficient braille and large print materials, difficulty with phone and video communication and limited staff training in deaf-blind communication.
3. **Technological Challenges:** Some of the technical challenges faced by libraries in the provision of inclusive services for the deaf-blind are in the use of incompatible assistive technologies, limited accessibility features in digital resources, insufficient digital literacy support and difficulty with e-book and audiobook accessibility.
4. **Staff and Training Challenges:** This includes limited staff training on deaf-blindness and accessibility, lack of ASL and tactile sign language skills, insufficient disability awareness, high staff turnover and training needs.
5. **Financial and Resource Challenges:** Limited funding for accessibility initiatives, insufficient resources for assistive technologies, difficulty securing grants and funding, limited community support and partnerships
6. **Attitudinal and Social Challenges:** Stigma and stereotypes surrounding deaf-blindness, lack of awareness and understanding, limited community engagement and outreach.
7. **Policy and Legislative Challenges:** Inconsistent accessibility standards and regulations, limited enforcement of accessibility laws, insufficient policy support for deaf-blind services and difficulty advocating for deaf-blind needs.

Acknowledging and addressing these challenges will thus enable libraries to work towards providing more inclusive services for deaf-blind individuals and promoting equal access to information and opportunities.

Conclusion

Inclusive library services for deaf-blind individuals are essential for promoting equal access to information, education, and social opportunities. Therefore, understanding the unique needs and challenges faced by deaf-blind individuals can help libraries implement tailored services and strategies to ensure seamless accessibility. The integration of accessible technologies, trained staff, and collaborative partnerships is a key component of inclusive library services. Consequently, adopting universal design principles and adapting to evolving technologies will further improve the library experience for deaf-blind patrons. Ultimately, inclusive library services for deaf-blindness reflect core values of librarianship, including equity, accessibility, and social responsibility. By fostering an inclusive environment, libraries

can empower themselves to better bridge the gap between information and isolation experienced by deaf-blind individuals.

Recommendations

For future action, the following are recommended:

1. The Librarian Registration Council of Nigeria and the National Library of Nigeria, in collaboration with other relevant authorities, should begin the practical implementation of the National standards for inclusive library services.
2. The government and other responsible authorities should increase funding for accessible technologies and staff training.
3. There should be deliberate attempts by Heads of Libraries to foster partnerships between libraries, deaf-blind organisations, and advocacy groups.
4. Heads of libraries should conduct ongoing research and evaluation to improve services.
5. Libraries should make sure to create awareness and inclusivity through community outreach and education.

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